

LOCAL GOVERNMENT ADMINISTRATION AND HEALTH CARE DELIVERY IN OTURKPO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BENUE STATE NIGERIA

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Abstract: Local government administration plays a crucial role in community development particularly in health care delivery. This study examined the effect of local government administration on health care service delivery in Oturkpo local government area of Benue State. Specifically, it examined the effect of local government administration on drug availability; prevention and control of diseases; and maternal and child health provision in Oturkpo local government area. Three research questions and hypotheses guided the study. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. Population of the study were the residents of the local council and they were 266,411. However, they were reduced to a researchable size of 400 through Taro Yamane Statistical formula. Analysis of the data was done through Mean score. Hypotheses of the study was done through Chi-square tool leading to the findings of the study. The study found that local government administration in Oturkpo Benue State has no significant positive effect on drug availability; prevention and control of diseases; and provision of maternal and child health in the area. The study concluded that even though it is a constitutional requirement in Nigeria for local councils to deliver health care to the localities, most of them are failing in that requirement. The study therefore recommended for adequate funding from higher authorities to the local councils to enable them fulfil their constitutional duties.

Keywords: Local government administration, health care delivery, Drug availability, Prevention and control of diseases, Maternal and child health.

Introduction

The complementary nature of local government administration is to reach rural dwellers, political organizations and socio-economic development (Akani, 2017). Constitutionally, local government is the lens through which higher levels of government view people at the grassroots; it is a barometer to enhance social service delivery to rural communities (Tiku, Obeten, & Onyenemerem, 2019). Consequently, grassroots administration is employed to describe the location of this governmental arrangement. Effective development of people must be adequately mobilized. The idea of local government was born out of the need to bring government closer to the people in rural areas and a mechanism to engender good governance in rural areas (Oluwatobi, 2019). The reasons for establishing local government are to bring good governance to rural areas so that local people can participate fully in the process of governance, for local services and speed the pace of socio-political development. Section 7 of the 1999 Constitution guaranteed a system of local government on democratic

principles and stipulates that the function of local government councils is to participate in developing their area (Abbas and Ahmad, 2012). Nebo & Chigbo (2015) opine that the relevance of the local government councils as the government at the grassroots is measured by the quality and quantity of services rendered to the rural dwellers. Local government is supposed to be the root of development in terms of dealings with the people which democracy is centred upon. Hence, local government is visibly seen as a co-agent of rural development and as a partner in progress with both state and federal governments in rural development.

Tiku, Obeten, & Onyenemerem, (2019) opined that the need for the creation of local government stems from the fact that rural areas require infrastructural development. As the closest government to the people, it is the responsibility of the local government to provide for the local populace, take care of their needs and develop their areas (Fajonyomi & Olu- Owolabi, 2013). According to Oyedele, Osezua, Abdulkareem, & Ishola (2017), the responsibilities of providing the local population with social and economic services needed for survival, quality of living and political participation fall within local government administration. The creation of local government in Nigeria was borne out of the need to engender aggressive infrastructural development and quality service delivery in rural areas (Sehinde, 2008). Local governments are therefore constitutionally empowered to construct and maintain rural roads, street lighting, water and drains, and other highways or such public facilities (Federal Government of Nigeria [FGN], 1999). Unfortunately, this was not to be as the system has witnessed all manner of abuse which manifests in a lack of financial autonomy and other undue interferences. In the opinion of Akani(2017), local government councils are today under the firm grip of the state government, manipulating them at the caprices of the governors through the compromised State Houses of Assembly. Under such circumstances, it becomes very obvious that there is not much the local administration can offer in terms of rural development since the state governors who have assumed “ownership” of the councils would not allow them access to their funds.

As a result of this development, there has been growing recognition of the importance of rural development as an instrument in the overall development of the contemporary developing world. This is because of the glaring gap between the rural and urban areas in terms of infrastructure, resource distribution, human resources development and employment, which has made rural development imperative (Ogbazi, 1982 in Zakariya’u, 2014). This imbalance has subjected the rural areas to a more disadvantaged economic position. It has induced rural–urban migration, thereby increasing the employment situation in the urban areas, while, simultaneously depriving the rural areas of their agricultural workforce (Zakariya’u, 2014). The failure of local government in the area of service delivery over the years has made the citizens lose faith and trust in local government administration as an institution in Nigeria. As a result of this development, most of the rural areas in Nigeria are in a pathetic state of development, even, some of the urban local government areas are also deficient in development. Some of these infrastructures where available, are left uncared for. The implication of this is that local governments in Nigeria have been consistent over the years in their failure to enhance their capacity to engage and mobilize human resources towards their needs. Local roads are left unrepaired, rural electricity is in a state of dilemma, rural health centres are dilapidated with the absence of drugs and necessary health personnel, rural boreholes and water pumps have no water, and rural water scheme/projects are deserted (Tolu, 2014). In the light of the above, this study examines the extent local governments have been able to

provide social services (health, education, etc) and basic infrastructural facilities (rural/farm roads, food markets, parks, rural electrification, potable water, etc) to the local communities.

Objectives of the Study

The study is aimed at examining the effect of local government administration on health care service delivery in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. However, specifically it investigated:

- i. the effect of Local Government Administration on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State
- ii. the effect of Local Government Administration in the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State.
- iii. the effect of Local Government Administration on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were made to guide the study.

- i. What is the effect of Local Government Administration on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State?
- ii. What effect does Local Government Administration have in the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State?
- iii. What is the effect of Local Government Administration on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State?

Conceptual Review

Local Government Administration

Oluwatobi (2019) defined local government as a political division of a country or (in a government framework) state, which comprises bylaws and has considerable organizing power over related issues, empowering the authorities to force charges or to apply work for endorsed reasons. The overseeing body of such substance is chosen or something else is locally chosen (Oluwatobi, 2019). Contributing to the author's view, a more inclusive definition of local government, and the one that captures the important records of local government, is contained in the 1976 guidelines for local Government Change. In that line, local government is defined as a government at the nearby level responsible to work out through an agent chambers, built up by law to work out powers inside characterized zones.

Local government in Nigeria is the third tier of government that is recognized by the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria with the state and federal government as the super ordinate government. This government in Nigeria plays commentary roles with the State and Federal governments in meeting the needs of the people which include infrastructural facilities (Okpata, 2004). Local government is seen as a public sector organization, the third tier government with assigned functions and responsibilities, administrative structure and financial management both for maintaining itself and rendering its statutory assigned functions to its citizens (Uguru, 2011). Local government authorities as a third tier of government in Nigeria are very important in the execution of both central and component government policies and programmes. It is the nearest government that deals with the problems of the masses of the country.

Community Development

Community development in this setting can be said to be a self-directional effort of the people, by the people, and for the people. Eleberi et al. (2014) defined community development as a legitimate process to foresee community advancement, improvement, and instructive strategy to tackle social activity and development. Hills (2011) implied a facilitated approach whereby the community individuals embrace programs and ventures in an arranged way to enhance the livelihood situation of the individuals dwelling in that society. Community development is defined by Rahim and Asnarulkhadi (2010) as

a process that leads to change in many aspects of community living which include social, economic, cultural as well as environmental. It is about continual improvement, first with the help of change agents and later, by the people themselves to bring about change in their lives, which ultimately improves their quality of life. Thus, the focus of the community development process is the people's involvement (hereafter the word "community" will be used) whereby the community members come together to take action collectively to meet their shared goal(s) or to generate solutions to overcoming shared problems. (p. 62)

Nonetheless, Rubin and Rubin (2001) defined community development "as a process which occurs when people strengthen the bonds within their neighborhoods, build social networks, and form their organisations to provide a long-term capacity for problem-solving (p. 3)". Rahim and Asnarulkhadi (2010) further stated that community members who can do something to enhance their quality of life are portrayed as having the ability to think, decide, plan, and to take action in determining their lives. Therefore, in any community development program, both economic and individual growth must be given equal attention so as to ensure that the process of community development achieves its due balance of continuity and sustainability. Operationally, community development is viewed as the individuals' initiative to find resolution to their individual and popular struggle, dependence on their own possessions such as potential, and to be assisted on or after enhancing execution of developmental projects.

Availability and Distribution of Drugs

One of the major intentions of the primary health care is to distribute and make the most common medicines available to the areas so as to control primary illness. Availability of drugs is often considered the most important element in quality of health care in rural African settings. The first is that rational drug management will ensure availability of drugs (Yiliang, 2019). If need is calculated on the basis of morbidity patterns, if essential drugs are supplied and managed effectively, and if medicines are prescribed according to rational professional standards, then drugs will be available (Yan & Tianmin, 2019). WHO proposes that essential medicines should be necessary for public health, and should be accessible at all times, and be applied to all levels of society in appropriate dosage forms. However, according to the World Health Report 2000, about one-third of the world's population still lacks access to essential medicines (Yang, Dib, Zhu, 2010).

Prevention and Control of Diseases

It covers a wide range of social and environmental interventions that are designed to benefit and protect individual people's health and quality of life by addressing and preventing the root causes of ill health, not just focusing on treatment and cure (Tartari, 2021). Disease control is when public health experts talk about controlling a disease, they mean reducing the number of new infections, the number of people currently

infected, and the number of people who become sick or die from a disease in local settings. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), infection prevention and control (IPC) is a scientific approach and practical solution designed to prevent harm caused by infection to patients and health workers. It is a subset of epidemiology, but also serves an essential function in infectious diseases, social sciences and global health (WHO, 2020). Effective IPC is a public health issue that is fundamental to patient safety and health system strengthening. The prevention of healthcare-associated infections (HAI), epidemics (including the 2013-2016 Ebola virus disease outbreak), and pandemics of international concern (For Example; the 2009 flu pandemic) are rooted in effective IPC measures. (WHO, 2016).

Maternal and Child Health

Maternal health refers to the health of women during pregnancy, childbirth and the postnatal period. Each stage should be a positive experience, ensuring women and their babies reach their full potential for health and well-being. Maternal and child health (MCH) care is the health service provided to mothers (women in their childbearing age) and children. The targets for MCH are all women in their reproductive age groups, i.e., 15 - 49 years of age, children, school-age population and adolescents. Every pregnancy and birth is unique. Addressing inequalities that affect health outcomes, especially sexual and reproductive health and rights and gender, is fundamental to ensuring all women have access to respectful and high-quality maternity care

Theoretical Framework

Momentum Theory:

Momentum theory (MT) is one of the most recent theories in health promotion propounded by Bonnie Raingruber (2013). Concepts within the theory include (1) momentum, (2) roadblocks to change, (3) forces that get the ball rolling, (4) forces that provide the ongoing impetus for change, (5) forces that help a person get past the plateaus where change seems to slow, and (6) habit patterns. Momentum is defined as the amount and forces required to improve the existing health system and establish new ones. As a result, engaging in health behavior and system improvement regularly has not only a self-sustaining aspect to it but public, private and foreign interventions as well. Momentum is also the case that, to initiate a health system change, a substantial amount of effort is required to ensure improvement in health outcomes. Momentum theory is diverse reaching multiple areas of health promotion, however, it fraction explains the link between government intervention, other forms of intervention and health outcomes. For instance, in its concept of momentum, it recognized public, private and foreign interventions as means by which health systems can improve. An improvement in the health system in turn brings about improvement in health outcomes. The roadblocks concept of the theory also recognized a lack of commitment to the public plans and policies, unhealthy implementation behaviors, and lack of money or resources as factors that interfere with improvement in the health system. This placed significant importance on spending and interventions from public, private and foreign agents as means to improve health systems and outcomes. The concept of forces that get the ball rolling, forces that provide on-going impetus for change, forces that help a person get past the plateaus where change seems to slow and habits patterns in momentum theory recognized intervention of different forms (e.g. coaching from healthcare providers, non-government organization, government, private sectors (foreign or domestic) including out-of-pocket spending as strong factors that contributes to improvement and promotion of the health system. Like the Health Belief Theory

(HBT) and Intervention-Based Theory (IBT), Momentum theory (MT) fractionally applies to the study under review in that it placed emphasis on different forms of health interventions and how the aforesaid interventions can promote the health system as well as the health outcomes. In practice, there are many ways with which health interventions can take place. For example, health interventions may be in the form of government spending, foreign and private donations, aid, health-education orientation, etc. Through these measures, health infrastructure, drugs, health seminars and conferences, and training of health personnel are provided for patient utilization which contributes significantly to the reduction or elimination of diseases and improvement in general health outcomes. Given the proposition of the MT, it can serve as a theoretical backup to this study which majorly intends to examine the impact of government spending on health outcomes in the Nigerian context with recognition of other health interventions obtainable in Nigeria.

Hypotheses

- i. Local Government Administration has no significant effect on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State
- ii. Local Government Administration has no significant effect on the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State.
- iii. Local Government Administration has no significant effect on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State.

Methodology

Participants and Area of Study

The research was carried out in Oturkpo local government area of Benue State. Participants in this study consisted of the residents of the local government area totaling 266, 411 based on 2022 population estimation by the National Population Commission. Because of the large population. However, the participants were reduced to a researchable size through Yamane formula thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N e^2}$$

Where: N = population, 1 = constant, e = Degree of error (i.e 5% or 0.05)

The sample size is computed thus:

$$n = \frac{266,411}{1 + 266,411 (0.05)^2}$$
$$n = \frac{266,411}{1 + 1683.75}$$
$$n = \frac{266,411}{1684.75} = 399.76$$

n = approximately 400

Therefore, the sample size is 400

Participants for this study therefore were 400 residents selected through purposive sampling. However, 340 questionnaires were filled appropriately and used for analysis.

Data Analysis

Empirical evidence for this study was obtained through the use of questionnaire. Likert scale was used to generate data from the questionnaire. The information was put in a weighted scale with numerical values attached to them in the questionnaire as follows: Strongly Agree = 5, Agree = 4, Undecided = 3, Disagree = 2 and Strongly Disagree = 1. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics involved computation of means and standard deviations from the responses of the respondents to the questionnaire items. The decision rule was to accept any item that has a mean score of 3.00 and above. The hypotheses were tested using chi-square statistical test.

Research question One: What is the effect of Local Government Administration on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State?

Table 1: Effect of Local Government Administration on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State

s/n	Items	SA	A	UD	DA	SD	FREQ	Mean	Remark
1	They help in sourcing necessary drugs needed in their health facilities	50	90	20	120	60	340	2.8	Rejected
2	They help in subsidizing the basic drugs needed for health service	60	85	15	140	40	340	2.9	Rejected
3	They finance the distribution and production of locally-made drugs	50	50	10	140	90	340	2.5	Rejected
4	They help to enforce strict distribution of family planning drugs to married women	40	110	10	120	40	340	2.7	Rejected
5	Local government administration helps to ensure the timely distribution of essential drugs in the primary health centers	60	85	15	140	40	340	2.9	Rejected

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 1 reviewed the respondents' responses on the effect of Local Government Administration on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. However, the result of the analysis indicates that majority of the respondents disagreed that local government administration contributed to the availability and distribution of medicine in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. All the five items under this variable show a very low mean (i.e. 2.8, 2.9, 2.5, 2.7 and 2.9) respectively. The assertion showed that the respondents did not affirm the statement.

Research question Two: What effect does Local Government Administration have in the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State?

Table 2: Effect Local Government Administration has in the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State

s/n	Item	SA	A	U	DA	SD	FREQ	Mean	Decision
1	Local government administration helped in the administration of oral polio vaccines	70	70	10	160	30	340	2.9	Rejected
2	They support health system in preserving vaccines to administer to the people	60	90	10	130	50	340	2.9	Rejected
3	Local government authorities intervene by providing vaccines whenever there is an outbreak of diseases	40	120	10	120	50	340	2.9	Rejected
4	They play an active role in the administration of Covid-19 vaccines for the rural dwellers	50	90	10	125	55	340	2.7	Rejected
5	Local government administration makes sure that vaccines get to the people at no cost	70	60	20	150	40	340	2.9	Rejected

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 2 shows the respondents' answers to research question two, as a result of the previously proposed research question two in this study. The result of the analysis indicates that the majority of the respondents disagreed that local government administration played positive roles in prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. All five items under this variable show a negative response (i.e. 2.9, 2.9, 2.9, 2.7 and 2.9) respectively. This means that the respondents were not firm in their conviction that local government administration played a role in the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State.

Research question Three: What is the effect of Local Government Administration on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State?

Table 3: Effect of Local Government Administration on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State

s/n	Items	SA	A	U	D	SD	FR	Mea	Decisi
					A		EQ	n	on
1	Local government administration plays an active part in the provision of maternal care service	50	115	5	110	60	340	2.9	Reject ed
2	The LG administration supports reducing the cost of antenatal service in the hospital	80	60	20	120	60	340	2.9	Reject ed
3	They help in treating the main causes and risk factors of health deficiencies among nursing mothers	60	70	30	80	100	340	2.6	Reject ed
4	They help to provide basic counseling services with regards to family planning and birth control among married women	50	80	10	125	65	340	2.5	Reject ed
5	Local government administration helps in subsidizing the family planning logistics	60	60	20	120	80	340	2.7	Reject ed

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 indicates the responses on the effect of Local Government Administration on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. The result of the analysis indicates that the majority of the respondents affirmed that the role of local government administration in the provision of maternal and child health, including family planning in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State is not sufficient. All the five items under this variable shows a negative response (i.e. 2.9, 2.9, 2.6, 2.5 and 2.7) which means low degree of acceptance of the questions asked.

Test of Hypotheses

This section is dedicated to the testing of hypotheses. The chi-square test was adopted for the study. The chi-square formula is: $\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$

Test of Hypothesis One

Statement of Hypothesis One

- i. Local Government Administration has no significant effect on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State

Table 4: Chi-square test

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.000(a)	6	.238
Likelihood Ratio	8.318	6	.216
Linear-by-Linear Association	.000	1	1.000
N of Valid Cases	4		

12 cells (100.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .25.

Source: Authors compilation SPSS Output

When reading this table we are interested in the results of the "**Pearson Chi-Square**" row. We can see here that $\chi(6) = 18.00$, $p = .238$. This tells us that Local Government Administration has no significant effect on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State

Test of Hypothesis Two

Statement of Hypothesis Two

- i. Local Government Administration has no significant effect in the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State.

Table 5: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	25.000(a)	12	.245
Likelihood Ratio	13.322	12	.346
Linear-by-Linear Association	.976	1	.323
N of Valid Cases	5		

a 20 cells (100.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .20.

Source: Authors compilation SPSS Output

The result indicated that $\chi(12) = 25.00$, $p = .245$. This tells us that Local Government Administration has no significant effect on the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Statement of Hypothesis Three

- i. Local Government Administration has no significant effect on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State.

Table 6: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	29.000(a)	12	.232
Likelihood Ratio	13.322	12	.346
Linear-by-Linear Association	.976	1	.323
N of Valid Cases	5		

a 20 cells (100.0%) have an expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .20.

Source: Authors compilation SPSS Output

The result indicated that $\chi(12) = 29.00, p = .232$. This tells us Local Government Administration has no significant effect on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State.

Results Presentation

- i. Local Government Administration has no significant effect on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. This goes to show that Local government administration has not helped significantly to ensure the timely distribution of essential drugs in the primary health centers.
- ii. Local Government Administration has no significant effect on the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. This implies that the Local council have not made enough effort to intervene by providing vaccine whenever there is an outbreak of diseases.
- iii. Local Government Administration has no significant effect on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. This indicated that Local government administration has not played an active role in the provision of maternal care service

Discussion of Findings

The finding revealed that Local Government Administration has no significant effect on drug availability in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. We can see here that $\chi(6) = 18.00, p = .238$. The finding is further substantiated by the data in Table 4.1 where the respondents were negative in their affirmation of the items. They rejected all the items from 1-5, which means that local government administration especially Otukpo LGA has not helped significantly in sourcing for necessary drugs needed in their health facilities, and they have not helped in subsidizing the basic drugs needed for maternal health service. Finance, distribution and production of locally made drugs are not being provided and they do not help to enforce strict distribution of family planning drugs to married women. They equally affirmed that Local government administration fails to ensure the timely distribution of essential drugs in the primary health centers. It can be seen that few drugs that are available in most of the primary health institutions are provided by donor agencies and NGOs. The result is in agreement with that of Sengupta (2015) who revealed that health expenditure taken alone does not have any impact on the health parameters.

The result of hypothesis two revealed that Local Government Administration has no significant effect on the prevention and control of diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. The result indicated that $\chi(12) = 25.00, p = .245$. From data in Table 4.2, we can equally observe that the respondents did not accept the fact that Local government administration helped in the administration of oral polio vaccines, that the Otukpo LGA support help system in preserving vaccines to administer to the people, that Local government authorities intervene by providing vaccine whenever there is an outbreak of diseases, and that they play active role in the administration of Covid-19 vaccines for the rural dwellers. The respondents who were in the majority rejected the fact that Local government administration makes sure that vaccines get to the people at no cost.

Lastly, the result showed that Local Government Administration has no significant effect on maternal and child health provision in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State. The result indicated that $\chi(12) = 29.00, p = .232$. This finding still falls in line with the outcome of the descriptive statistics in Table 4.3, where the majority of the respondents did not accept any item in the table. The respondents were of the view that Local government administration plays low active part in the provision of maternal care service, that the LG administration does

not support reducing the cost of antenatal service in the hospital, and that Otukpo LGA does not help in treating the main causes and risk factors of health deficiencies among nursing mothers. The respondents firmly rejected the fact that the local council help to provide basic counseling services as regards family planning and birth control among married women and that Local government administration helps in subsidizing the family planning logistics.

Conclusion

Constitutional provision in Nigeria has it that local government administration has the responsibility of providing primary health service however, the results have not been the case. The study concludes that Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State has not significantly provided maternal and child health, including family planning, provision of immunization against major diseases in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State and making available and distribution of medicine in Benue State.

Recommendations

- i. Adequate funding for local governments that would allow for community health education. The citizens need enlightenment on their health rights. This will allow them to make suggestions and ideas for the system.
- ii. Governments should redirect resources for health care from curative services to preventive services to improve the primary health care infrastructures, encourage the migration of health workers from urban areas to rural areas and provide an acceptable level of health care services for all, thereby reducing the gross inequality in the health status of the people.
- iii. There is a need for the maintenance of minimum health standards, improved housing conditions, water, environment, sanitation and food supply for the sustenance of good health conditions. There is a need therefore for the local government as well as other tiers of government to increase the allocation of the health sector.

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